

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development,
training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

Assessment of available data from external sources

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Traffic and accident data are of paramount importance for the advancement of research and development of safe and efficient automated driving systems (ADS). Such data are needed towards in-depth understanding of traffic dynamics, environmental effects and modelling inter-relations and interactions of traffic participants. The safety argumentation, which is the holy grail of ADS research and development, is also dependent on the existence of such data. Scenario-based validation requires testing on a set of driving scenarios, selected to assess the safety case of the ADS. To this aim, SYNERGIES targets the development of a platform, including a scenario dataspace and a marketplace, which will provide scenarios and tools to facilitate the testing of ADS. The first step towards this goal is the collection of relevant data sources to be used for scenario creation. These sources include both existing datasets and data that will be collected and generated in SYNERGIES.

The present deliverable is the outcome of task T3.2 of SYNERGIES and provides a systematic overview, qualification and analysis of the state-of-the-art exemplary datasets, which may be related to the development and evaluation of ADS. First, a systematic literature review was performed to identify existing published datasets that are relevant to the scope of SYNERGIES towards scenario generation and extraction, including accident datasets. The dataset listing was complemented by datasets coming from relevant projects and partner-owned datasets. Subsequently, the found datasets were qualified based on the high-level data qualification methodology designed within SYNERGIES. Finally, the qualifying datasets were analysed based on taxonomies designed to enable the extraction of information that can be leveraged for visualization, filtering, and clustering processes. Metadata were generated to facilitate the use of these datasets by the rest of the project and the general community.

This deliverable concludes with a list of qualified datasets which are accessible and available to be used in SYNERGIES. The dataset listing is provided together with metadata and source information and shall serve not only the objectives of SYNERGIES tasks, but also those of the general community towards more efficient retrieval, selection, and usage of data for automated mobility applications. The dataset listing provided has been made within the scope of SYNERGIES and based on available datasets from the community and by different project partners. There may be further datasets which are available, such as industry partners own collected data, or even future datasets that may arise, which are not captured in the list.

Main outcomes

The outcomes of this task include:

1. Qualified dataset listing for SYNERGIES, including real and synthetic driving datasets, and accident datasets
2. Analysis of dataset listing, based on designed taxonomies and overview of the existing dataset coverage
3. Metadata for each qualified dataset

Keywords: automated mobility datasets, systematic review, taxonomy, qualification, metadata

2 INTRODUCTION

The SYNERGIES project aims to build a scenario dataspace, including both real and virtual scenarios, with the vision to facilitate testing and validation of cooperative, connected and automated mobility (CCAM) systems. For the purpose of scenario creation, the availability of data is crucial. SYNERGIES relies on existing datasets on three folds. First, as a pool of data that can be directly used for scenario identification and extraction (T5.2) as well as for training algorithms for synthetic data generation (T3.4, T3.5) and scenario generation (T5.3). Second, as an indicator of the current state of scenario coverage in existing datasets, which shall guide the data collection and generation processes foreseen within the project (T3.3, T3.4, T3.5). Finally, such data shall be used for the design and development of tools (WP4) that will eventually form the marketplace of the SYNERGIES Platform. Apart from the aforementioned use cases, the datasets can be used for the extraction of probability distributions of the scenario parameters, which may be of significance for other tasks of the project.

The objective of task T3.2 is the investigation of existing data sources and their qualification for their potential to be used in SYNERGIES. The data sources include open datasets available online, datasets from key EU projects, as well as datasets that partners may provide. Special attention was paid to the collection of accident data as these can help study and reproduce challenging scenarios. The above objective has been divided into five sub-objectives which have determined five T3.2 sub-tasks respectively (**Figure 1**):

1. Review of the state-of-the-art of existing datasets
2. Design of taxonomies to describe datasets
3. Qualification of existing datasets for potential to create scenarios
4. Analysis of qualified datasets and current scenario coverage
5. Generation of metadata for qualified datasets

Figure 1 Steps for the assessment of datasets from external sources

The present deliverable presents the work performed in the framework of the task T3.2 to meet the above objectives. The output of the task is a dataset listing which reports the name and source of each qualified dataset as well as its metadata. This deliverable shall be used by:

- WP3 tasks (T3.3/4/5) to inform and guide their data collection and generation campaigns towards filling gaps in the existing body of datasets.
- WP4 tasks to provide a pool of datasets for the development of tools
- WP5 tasks to provide a pool of qualified datasets that can be used for scenario extraction and generation
- Other WPs and tasks for the extraction of scenario parameters probability distributions

The work of task T3.2 was delivered in close collaboration and consideration of: i) the SYNERGIES technical and interoperability requirements derived in WP2, D2.2 [2], ii) the requirements of WP5

on the Scenario Source Data (SSD) OmegaPrime format [3], and iii) the qualification methodology provided by T3.1 and described in D3.1 [4].

The rest of this document is structured as follows. Chapter 3 describes the methodology for the review of the datasets from external sources. Chapter 4 presents the taxonomies derived for the analysis of the datasets. Chapter 5 is dedicated to the application of the qualification methodology to identify and screen out datasets that do not fulfill the quality requirements of SYNERGIES. Chapter 6 presents the analysis of the qualified datasets based on the designed taxonomies. Chapter 7 covers and groups the different metadata extracted in the previous analysis. Finally, the complete list of all qualified datasets with their metadata is provided in Chapter 8.

3 REVIEW OF THE STATE-OF-THE-ART OF EXISTING DATASETS

This chapter presents the methodology that was followed for the identification of relevant datasets from external sources and the relevant findings. The review focused on the collection of both driving data and accident report data. As *driving data*, we define data coming either from the real world or synthetically generated, which contain time-series information and aim to capture real-world traffic situations such as driving manoeuvres, critical situations, near-accidents, and accidents. This category can include naturalistic driving studies (NDSs), telemetry data, and traffic observations (including aerial perspective data). As *accident report data* we define datasets that describe dedicated accidents collected either on-scene or off-scene by police, dedicated investigators, or insurers, and come from reports, measurements, or in-vehicle electronic data recorders. The consideration of accident report data, in situations which are within the operational driving domain (ODD) are requested to comply with international regulations¹ on ADS and before requesting the in-service authorisation of Automated Road Transport System in some countries². For this reason, accident report datasets were considered as relevant datasets by SYNERGIES partners. Accident report datasets are very important from the safety argumentation point of view because they cover situations where there is a clear risk to the drivers, vehicle occupants or other road users involved, and where an ADS shall not increase the level of risk.

3.1 Methodology for datasets review

The review of state-of-the-art datasets for ADS included three sources of available datasets, namely:

- i) Open datasets, publicly available
- ii) Datasets from relevant projects
- iii) Datasets from SYNERGIES partners

For the collection of publicly available driving datasets, a systematic review of literature and online sources was conducted following a two-step process. First, existing published reviews of datasets for ADS were identified through web search with relevant keywords such as "automated mobility", "driving data", and "review". In particular, the reviews from [5] and [6] were selected due to being the most recent and comprehensive peer-reviewed publications in the field. Second, web search with given keywords was performed to identify datasets not reported in the used reviews based on the methodology proposed in [5]. Additionally, driving datasets from relevant projects or owned by SYNERGIES partners were collected and listed by the involved partners. The collection of accident report datasets was based on the expertise of SYNERGIES partners who provided sources of open datasets or relevant projects which have generated such data. Datasets containing only accidents were classified as reported accident

¹ International Regulations on vehicles equipped with ADS are: 1 - United Nations regulation 157 on level 3 ADS on highway, 2 - European regulation 2022/1426 on level 4 ADS.

² National regulations like AFGBV in Germany (https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/afgbv/_1.html) and LOM law in France (link to Automated Road Transports legal framework : <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/transport-routier-automatise-connecte>)

datasets, while datasets which aimed at collecting real-world data, but may also contain some accident situations, were classified as driving datasets.

After the identification of the preliminary dataset listing following the above approach, a screening phase was performed to exclude datasets that were not relevant to the objective of SYNERGIES for scenario creation. This phase involved only the identified driving datasets. Examples include datasets that were collected merely for specific tasks such as object detection for perception testing that provided sensor recordings without temporal sequence, or datasets that focused on driver behaviour and did not capture traffic information. Therefore, two exclusion criteria were devised to screen out driving datasets that could be directly identified as not relevant to SYNERGIES:

- Datasets that did not include time-series (temporal information): Such datasets (e.g. providing only selected frames but not in temporal sequence) cannot provide trajectory information of the participating agents, hence they cannot be used for scenario creation.
- Datasets that did not include traffic annotations: Datasets that provided only raw sensor data without any post-processing for object detection and classification, or datasets that did not provide traffic-related annotations were discarded as they cannot be directly used for trajectory extraction and scenario creation.

Moreover, an additional exclusion criterion was applied to all datasets (driving and accident report):

- Datasets that were not accessible: When datasets were clearly not accessible during the review phase, they were directly excluded from the listing.

It should be noted that the list of datasets from external sources identified through the above process may not be exhaustive, as several other datasets may exist, e.g. owned by industry partners (Tier 1s, OEMs) which are not publicly reported.

3.2 Review results

Based on the aforementioned review process, a total of 160 datasets were identified. The vast majority (149) are driving datasets, from which 104 are related to data collected in the real-world and 45 are synthetically generated. From the ones collected in the real-world, 95 are publicly available, 7 are related to relevant projects, and 2 were contributed by SYNERGIES partners. All synthetic datasets are publicly available. Moreover, a total of 11 accident report datasets were identified, 4 of which are publicly available and 7 are related to relevant projects (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2 Overview of found datasets

In total, 12 projects were identified as potential sources of data relevant to SYNERGIES and were considered in our review. Additionally, 2 partners (RENAULT and STELLANTIS) contributed with own datasets. The list of project and partner datasets is presented in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Projects/partners with relevant datasets for SYNERGIES

Project/partner name	Dataset type
UDRIVE	Driving
Hi-Drive	Driving
L3Pilot	Driving
Roadview	Driving
EVENTS	Driving
SHRP2	Accident report
GIDAS	Accident report
IGLAD	Accident report
TASC	Accident report
BAAC	Accident report
VOISEUR	Accident report
ADSCene	Accident report
RENAULT (L1-L2 ADAS)	Driving
STELLANTIS	Driving

The vast majority of the driving datasets were published within the last 5 years. As **Figure 3** depicts, an increasing trend is observed in the publication of new driving datasets, a fact that reflects the underlining research activity in the domain of AD. This manifests both in the real and in the synthetic datasets publication trend.

Figure 3 Number of datasets per year of publication

Accidents are extremely rare phenomena requesting long-lasting driving before occurring. That's why the accident datasets need a collection time span of at least one year to be relevant. All accident datasets considered in the project fulfil this requirement and always collect new accident scenarios each year. For this reason, accident report datasets are significantly fewer and cannot fulfil the same requirements as recorded real-world driving data. Due to this reason, all identified accident report datasets were considered in our preliminary data listing without screening and directly subjected to the qualification phase. These datasets are very different from each other in terms of region, injuries, representativeness, and of the accident reconstruction process. The detailed analysis of the accident report datasets that passed the qualification are presented in Chapter 6.

3.3 Conclusions

Our review highlights the existence of a vast number of datasets relevant for ADS, that could be potentially used in SYNERGIES. Most datasets record (or simulate) driving traffic situations, while, in contrast, only few accident report datasets are available. In order to gain an informed overview of the datasets field, their coverage and potential for SYNERGIES, the identified preliminary data listing which was formed after the review stage needs further analysis. The datasets quality is one of the most critical factors for their adoption in SYNERGIES. Hence, the datasets were first qualified based on the methodology described in D3.1 [4] and the results of the qualification are discussed in Chapter 5. Another challenge identified during the review process was that each dataset has been recorded under different setups, traffic and environment conditions, which hinders a comprehensive analysis, comparison and overview of the field. This is demonstrated in Chapter 6 which presents the detailed analysis of the qualified datasets. To facilitate such an analysis, dedicated taxonomies for driving and accident report datasets were designed which is discussed in Chapter 4. The qualification and analysis of the datasets generated metadata (Chapter 7) that shall guide their selection and usage by SYNERGIES partners and the community.

4 DATASETS TAXONOMIES

One of the difficulties encountered during the datasets review process was that each dataset reports the recorded information in a different way. However, all datasets present similarities and common attributes that need to be identified to gain an overview and understand their potential for SYNERGIES. To capture the commonalities and important information in the datasets, two taxonomies were designed, one for driving and one for accident report datasets. The reason for two taxonomies was the intrinsic differences in recorded signals and attributes between these two types of datasets.

The taxonomy design followed a three-step process:

- i) Draft taxonomies were designed including the expected categories, attributes and corresponding values based on the experience of the involved partners and the literature review.
- ii) The taxonomies were updated during the process of parsing the found datasets with additional attributes and/or values found in these datasets.
- iii) The taxonomies were further improved through feedback from WP5 (scenario generation methodology and process), on the requirements of input data for scenario creation and from the qualification methodology provided in D3.1 [4].

It should be noted that the selected attributes for the design of the taxonomies were based on the information identified in the collected datasets and the feedback from other WPs and it is not an exhaustive taxonomy covering any possible attribute of the ADS field. The two taxonomies are presented in detail below.

To support consistency and integration across work packages, these taxonomies will need to be mapped and linked with the scenario taxonomy established in WP5. As part of Task 5.5, an ODD and behaviour-based taxonomy has been provided, reviewed, and agreed upon by partners. This taxonomy is grounded in established standards, namely ISO 34503 for ODD taxonomy and BSI PAS 1891 for behaviour taxonomy. High-level mapping examples of the ODD and behaviour related attributes will be provided in subsequent sections of this report.

4.1 Driving data taxonomy

The taxonomy of the driving datasets was designed to support the most important information required for their principal purpose in SYNERGIES, which is the identification, extraction and generation of scenarios. At high level, the driving data taxonomy includes the following 6 categories (**Figure 4**). Each category is further described in the following subsections.

- Sensing domain
- Sensors
- Annotations
- Environment
- Size
- Driving mode/Simulation tool

Figure 4 Driving datasets taxonomy at high-level

4.1.1 Sensing domain

The sensing domain describes the viewpoint of the data based on the location of the sensors used for the data collection. The sensing domain attributes included in the taxonomy are the following (**Figure 5**):

- Ego vehicle: Sensors are attached to the ego vehicle and record from the ego viewpoint
- Other vehicle: Sensors are attached to one or more vehicles (except for the ego) connected or not
- Infrastructure: Sensors are attached to static infrastructure
- Drones: Sensors are attached to drone(s)
- Vulnerable road users (VRUs): Sensors are attached to VRUs, e.g. pedestrians

Datasets may include more than one sensing domain. This is the case for datasets tackling V2X applications.

Figure 5 Sensing domain taxonomy for driving datasets

For the sensing domain, aligning the dataset taxonomy with the scenario taxonomy established in WP5 requires mapping the sensing-related attributes to the corresponding attributes defined in ISO 34503, specifically under the "dynamic elements" attribute. In this alignment:

- "VRU" maps to the "traffic agents" subattribute within the "dynamic elements" attribute
- "Other vehicle" also corresponds to the "traffic agents" subattribute under "dynamic elements" attribute
- "Ego vehicle" aligns with the "subject vehicle" subattribute within the "dynamic elements" attribute

4.1.2 Sensors

In all datasets, data collection was performed with the use of a sensor suite. One or a combination of sensor modalities were used for the data recording and each dataset provided the recorded data per sensor modality. The sensors category refers to the types of sensor modalities used. The specification of each sensor modality and the setup description are not reported. The sensor modalities included in the taxonomy are the following (**Figure 6**):

- Camera (including any type of camera – RGB, fisheye, 3d)
- LIDAR
- Radar
- IMU/GNSS
- Varifocal lense
- Localization sensor
- Night vision
- Vehicle data (this is not sensor data per se but is reported here as it best fits)

Figure 6 Sensors taxonomy for driving datasets

4.1.3 Annotations

Annotations in datasets are essential for enabling humans and algorithms, including machine learning models, to interpret and learn from data effectively. Annotations serve as labels or metadata that define specific attributes, structures, or behaviours within a dataset, helping algorithms and users understand patterns and relationships. They are widely used in fields such as computer vision, natural language processing, and the training, validation, and testing of ADS models.

For instance, in computer vision, annotations can include labels like bounding boxes (2D and 3D), semantic segmentation masks and key points for tasks such as object detection, image classification/segmentation, pose estimation, etc. Annotations of driveable areas and lane markings are essential for ADS navigation. Similarly, traffic sign annotations help training models to recognize and interpret road signs. In the context of SYNERGIES, annotations are of paramount important for the extraction of agents' trajectories, the accurate map positioning and the scene interpretation.

Annotations vary based on the dataset's purpose and complexity, ranging from simple labels to detailed spatial, temporal, and contextual information. The richness and quality of annotations significantly influence the performance of machine learning models, making them a cornerstone of effective model training and evaluation. In the driving dataset taxonomy, the following annotation types were considered (**Figure 7**):

- Bounding boxes (2D/3D)
- Semantic segmentation
- 2D panoptic segmentation
- Lane markings/road paintings
- Drivable area
- Traffic signs
- Road condition (wet, snow etc)
- Key points (human pose)
- Camera pose
- Anomalies/outliers
- Trajectories

Figure 7 Annotations taxonomy for driving datasets

4.1.4 Environment

This category considers aspects related to the environment conditions of the recorded data and includes the following attributes (**Figure 8**):

- Geographical location: The country or city where the data were recorded
- Road type: The type of road as urban, rural, highway, intersection, roundabout
- Visibility: The time of day of the recording (day, night, dawn/dusk) and/or reported information about visibility (visibility clear, visibility reduced)

- Weather: The weather conditions during recording (clear weather, rain, fog, snow, wind)
- Road state: The state of the road during recording (road dry, road wet, road ice)

Figure 8 Environment taxonomy for driving datasets

For the environment domain, aligning the dataset taxonomy with the scenario taxonomy established in WP5 requires mapping the environment-related attributes to the corresponding attributes defined in ISO 34503, specifically under "*scenery elements*" or "*environmental conditions*". In this alignment:

- "*Visibility*" maps to the subattributes within "*environmental conditions*" attribute
- "*Road type*" and "*Road state*" correspond to the "*drivable area*" subattribute under "*scenery elements*" attribute
- "*Geographical location*" aligns with the "*zones*" subattribute within "*scenery elements*" attribute
- "*Weather*" corresponds to the "*weather*" subattribute under "*environmental conditions*" attribute

4.1.5 Size

The size category considers attributes that describe different aspects that relate to the size of the dataset. These include information regarding the (Figure 9):

- Number of scenes
- Scene length
- Number of annotated frames (camera, LIDAR, and/or radar)

- Annotation sampling frequency (camera, LIDAR, and/or radar)
- Amount of trajectories
- Data storage size

Figure 9 Size taxonomy for driving datasets

4.1.6 Driving mode/Simulation environment

The last taxonomy attribute differs between real-world and synthetic driving datasets. For real-world datasets, it refers to the driving mode of the ego vehicle. Driving mode concerns only datasets that have been collected from an ego vehicle sensing domain and reflects whether the ego vehicle was driven manually (human driver) or by an ADS. About half of the datasets did not report this information directly, however, in most cases it could be derived/guessed indirectly from the data collection description, e.g. by the vehicle model reported. The driving mode taxonomy describes the above with two attributes as automated and manual (Figure 10).

For synthetic driving datasets the last taxonomy attribute refers to the simulation environment used for the execution of the scenarios and the data recording. The information about the simulation environment used is important to report as it provides clarity over the realism of the collected data and depends on the simulation environment graphics and properties. Moreover, it is useful for gaining an overview of the existing simulators and their prevalence. The simulation environment attribute does not contain any child attributes.

Figure 10 Driving mode taxonomy for real driving datasets

4.2 Accident report data taxonomy

To increase road safety, the analysis of accident reports exists in several countries. Accident scenarios are then often stored and capitalised in databases but it is common that these databases are not available. Very few international initiatives to increase road safety share accident scenarios and build international datasets. The definition of a standard taxonomy allows to describe all relevant parameters for understanding the accident, its causes and its consequences, generally described in injury terms. At high level the accident data taxonomy is divided into 5 categories (Figure 11):

- Administrative information

- Traceability
- Severity
- Environment
- Static & Dynamic Objects

Figure 11 High-level accident report datasets taxonomy

For each category, sub items are defined and are discussed in detail in the next sections.

4.2.1 Administrative information

Administrative information includes the following attributes:

- Validation status: It represents the validation status of the accident scenario. At first, when coding an accident scenario, the status is DRAFT. During the writing of the accident scenario description, its status remains DRAFT. When all the information has been entered, the user indicates that their accident scenario is ready to be reviewed. The status of the accident scenario will then change to READY. During the review process made by the dedicated expert team, if an issue arises that requires significant changes, the status of the accident scenario changes to FEEDBACK. This status is accompanied by a list of detected errors so that the user can rework their accident scenario. Once the errors have been corrected, the user returns the accident scenario to READY. If no mistake is detected during the review, the status of the accident scenario turns to VALIDATED. This process is depicted in Figure 12.
- Country: Name of the country, where the accident took place.
- Main accident cause: Event having caused the accident situation
- Weight: The representativeness at national level for the associated year of this case.

Figure 12 Validation process for accident scenarios

Figure 13 Administrative information taxonomy for accident report datasets

4.2.2 Severity information

This part is associated to each accident case regarding the injury severity of the persons involved. These parameters allow to characterize the injury severity relevance of the accident scenario. The injury severity can be extracted from the official injury reported in the accident, generally reported by the police (as MAIS data is not commonly available).

- Killed: Number of deaths in the accident.
- Severely injured: Number of severely injured persons involved in the accident.
- Slightly injured: Number of involved persons suffering only slight injuries in the accident.
- Not injured: Number of involved persons having no injury in the accident.

Figure 14 Severity information taxonomy for accident report datasets

4.2.3 Traceability information

Traceability parameters allow to clearly identify a dataset's pedigree³ and constitutes a crucial parameter of its quality. Traceability includes the following attributes:

- Source: Name of the project, initiative or owner institute, to contact to get access to the accident report dataset. In most cases, the raw information (accident reports) is not directly accessible for GDPR reasons or with limited or licensed access.
- Database: Name of the database where accident cases are stored (sometimes Source and Database have the same name, e.g. GIDAS).
- Identifier: For each dataset, each accident case has a unique id that allows its identification and access (for the dedicated "Source") to its coded characteristics.

³ **Pedigree**: The history or provenance of a person or thing (here data), especially as conferring distinction. The word "pedigree" include the idea of data quality in addition to origin and line of descent.

Figure 15 Traceability taxonomy for accident report datasets

4.2.4 Environment

The environment taxonomy describes the environmental characteristics of the accident scene. The same taxonomy as in driving data was used.

4.2.5 Static and Dynamic objects

This last category contains all the relevant parameters to describe the accident report cases, namely the traffic participants⁴ involved, their behaviours⁵ (including acceleration, braking, lane change etc), the pre-collision configuration, and the type of participants or road users involved.

Figure 16 Static and dynamic objects taxonomy for accident report datasets

This domain aligns with the scenario taxonomy used in WP5 through mappings to ISO 34503 and BSI Flex 1891. In this alignment:

- "*Participants*" corresponds to the "*dynamic elements*" attribute in ISO 34503
- "*Behaviour*" is described by the behaviour taxonomy outlined in BSI Flex 1891
- "*Traffic state*" maps to the "*dynamic state*" attribute within ISO 34503

Each category can be assigned with given values depicted in

Table 2:

⁴ "Traffic participants" or "Actors" are road user or objects that are the subjects of the actions

⁵ Behaviours or Actions is an evolution of a state variable of a traffic participant whatever it is, i.e. a vehicle, a driver, a pedestrian,

...

Table 2 Elements of static and dynamic objects

Participants	Behaviour	Pre-collision configuration	Traffic state
Animals	Sideslip	Rear-end	OTHER VEHICLE
Objects	Rollover	Sideswipe	SMOOTH
Regular Road User ⁶	Embedded ⁷	Overtaking	HEAVY
Special Road User ⁸	Collision	Head-on	SATURATED
VRU ⁹	Acceleration	Turning	
	Braking	Backing	
	Deceleration	Lane-changing	
	Lane Change	Crossing	
	Shift		
	Turning		
	Zigzag		

⁶ Regular Road Users are Non vulnerable road vehicles categorized in types (e.g. M1) and whose driver has to comply to the rules of the road.

⁷ Embedded : behaviour of two traffic participants being stuck one in the other, e.g. a pedestrian & bicycle forming a cyclist, or 2 cars after an accident.

⁸ Special Road Users are non VRUs subject to special rules of the road, like law enforcement entities, firetrucks, ambulances, agricultural vehicles ...

⁹ VRUs are non protected road users, i.e. Pedestrian, Bicyclists, Motorcyclists, and users of Personal Mobility Devices

5 QUALIFICATION OF DATASETS COMING FROM EXTERNAL SOURCES

After the identification of the relevant datasets listing from external sources as described in Chapter 3, the next step was their qualification to ensure they meet the quality criteria of SYNERGIES. The methodology that was followed for the qualification of the datasets was derived in the task T3.1 and is reported in D3.1 [4]. It is a hierarchical methodology built on two levels, a high-level one and a detailed one. Only the high-level methodology is considered here for two reasons:

1. Due to the various possibilities that the datasets provide, which extend beyond the scenario identification application to e.g. development of tools for data annotation (object detection, tracking etc) and more, it was considered best to maintain a more generic screening approach and leave the detailed qualification to the datasets users.
2. Based on the available resources of T3.2, a prioritisation on the application of the methodology had to be done, considering the large amount of identified datasets.

The detailed methodology will be applied by other tasks, outside of T3.2, on the datasets selected for the task needs to ensure high quality of the used data.

5.1 Summary of the high-level qualification methodology

The high-level qualification methodology comprises five criteria which are explained below. For further details on the methodology, the reader is referred to D3.1 [4]. The found datasets were assessed against these criteria, and a True/False value was assigned for each criterion. To ensure data quality, datasets had to comply to all five criteria. To this end, datasets were qualified as PASS if all values were true, while if at least one criterion was false, the datasets were assigned a FAIL outcome.

Coverage

The coverage criterion is to ascertain whether the dataset under analysis incorporates essential contextual data, such as timestamps and geolocation, across all sensor data. The purpose of this process is to ensure that the data can be properly aligned and interpreted in time and space. To pass the coverage criteria a dataset must contain:

- Frames (for all sensors) must include timestamp information
- Frames (for all sensors) must include location information

Accessibility

Accessibility evaluates the ease with which the dataset can be accessed and utilized. This includes the availability of both historical and real-time data, the compatibility of data formats with standard tools, the scalability of the hosting infrastructure, and the clarity of access permissions. These are encapsulated in the following requirements:

- Availability (Historical Data): True/False (if the timestamp attribute exists in the dataset)
- Availability (Real-time Data): True/False (if the location attribute exists in the dataset)
- Format Compatibility: True/False (if the format of the dataset is in the acceptable format list)
 - Lidar pointclouds format: PCD, PLY, LAS, E57
 - Camera data format: JPEG, PNG/HEIF, BMP, TIFF, RAW, MP4, H264/265 MPEG/AVI, MKV

- Annotations format: TXT, JSON, XML/YAML
- Infrastructure and Scalability: True/False (if the platform can handle multiple concurrent calls for big data extraction)
- Access Permissions: True/False (if the provider/platform documented the access permissions clearly and transparently)

Documentation

Proper documentation is essential for understanding the dataset structure, ensuring its correct usage, and facilitating reproducibility. The documentation criterion considers the availability of supporting materials including:

- Codebook availability
- Format documentation
- Website documentation
- Publications

Metadata

Metadata includes detailed information about how the data were collected, processed, and annotated. Comprehensive metadata are vital for evaluating data quality, verifying its origin and enabling informed decisions during data analysis. The metadata criterion defines the requirements on the availability and completeness of the metadata of a given dataset:

- Availability (information that describes the data in the dataset and how the dataset is collected or generated)
- Completeness (descriptive metadata, such as information about the authors, version and date of creation, provenance metadata, data sources used for collection or processing history, and annotation metadata, such as object or scenario labelling)

Licensing

The Licensing criterion defines the legal permissions and restrictions associated with dataset usage. Clear and permissive licensing ensures that partners can use the data following confidentiality rules and license conditions (e.g. data protection, liability) for their intended purposes. The data license status was categorized into the five below cases:

- Unknown - FALSE
- Closed - FALSE
- Restricted to partners - TRUE
- Open with restrictions - TRUE
- Open - TRUE

5.2 Datasets qualification results

From the 160 datasets identified through the review process, 89 datasets in total were disqualified after applying the high-level qualification methodology (**Table 3**).

Table 3 Qualification outcomes per dataset category

	Real driving	Synthetic driving	Accident	Total
PASS	54	6	9	69
FAIL	48	39	2	89

The majority of the datasets were disqualified either on the grounds of the coverage criterion (missing timestamps or location information) or on the grounds of license and accessibility criteria (license closed, unknown, download link inaccessible). The detailed statistics for disqualification are presented in **Table 4**. This table shows the overall number of cases where criteria were not met. In some cases, a dataset did not meet several criteria.

Table 4 Detailed disqualification results

Reason	Criterion	Real driving	Synthetic driving	Accident report
no timestamps	Coverage	9	17	
no locations	Coverage	14	19	2
wrong format	Accessibility	1		
no codebook/documentation	Documentation	10	7	
no metadata	Metadata	2	2	1
license closed	License	7		
license unknown	License		6	
download link inaccessible	License	12	10	
download platform unsafe	License	5	1	

In total, 69 datasets passed the qualification process, of which 54 are real driving, 6 are synthetic driving and 9 are accident report datasets. Two datasets related to EU projects (Hi-Drive and EVENTS) have not been considered since their information and access rights are not yet available. The complete list of qualified datasets is provided in Chapter 8.

6 ANALYSIS OF QUALIFIED DATASETS

The 69 datasets that passed the qualification process, were subsequently analysed based on the defined taxonomies (Chapter 4). Real and synthetic driving datasets are presented together despite their intrinsic source differences, due to the limited number of qualified synthetic datasets. This chapter is dedicated to the presentation of the analysis results and conclusions.

6.1 Driving datasets

As discussed in Chapter 5, 54 real driving and 6 synthetic datasets qualified and were considered for further analysis. Using the designed taxonomy (section 4.1), the information regarding the six main features of the datasets was extracted and collected. This included information regarding the sensing domain, the sensors used, the annotations provided, the environment conditions covered, the size, and the driving mode (for real datasets) or the simulation tool (for synthetic datasets). It was not uncommon that datasets did not explicitly provide information regarding all those attributes and their sub-categories. Only if the information was explicit or could be derived with confidence from the documentation, was it considered in the analysis.

6.1.1 Sensing domain

All datasets reported their data collection process which, among others, described the location where the sensors were mounted for the recording. The sensors' location defines the sensing domain of the dataset, that is the point-of-view from which the data were collected. The most common sensing domain presented in the found datasets is that of the ego vehicle (E), which means that the sensors are mounted on the ego vehicle and the recorded data reflect its viewpoint. Several datasets were recorded using sensors mounted on infrastructure (I). Other found sensing domains include drones (D), pedestrians (P) and a second vehicle (V) which had sensors mounted. However, their presence is much less dominant compared to the ego sensing domain (**Figure 17**).

Figure 17 Driving datasets sensing domains

Most of the datasets use only one sensing domain, e.g. only ego or only infrastructure, however, 11 datasets combine two or more sensing domains. These datasets were collected with the objective to target V2X applications and are tagged here as V2X datasets. None of these datasets included connectivity between the sensing domains. **Figure 18** illustrates in more detail the sensing domain combinations that these datasets cover. In particular, the majority (10) of the datasets utilized a combination of one or two vehicles together with infrastructure. Five datasets presented other sensing domain combinations. It was observed that V2X is addressed to a larger extent in the synthetic datasets (four out of six synthetic datasets are V2X), presumably due to the fact that it is easier to apply within a simulation environment.

Figure 18 Driving datasets V2X sensing domain combinations

It is interesting to observe that the drone datasets cover a small portion of the dataset space, however, they would offer great potential for scenario creation as they provide the most complete view of the scene (bird-eye view). On the other hand, data collected from an ego vehicle or infrastructure provide a much finer level of detail of the traffic and the environment. At the same time, ego-based collected data can cover longer scenes compared to drones and static infrastructure. The combination of sensing domains could gain from their complementary advantages towards richer and more complex scenario creation, a potential that SYNERGIES could explore through the foreseen data collection campaigns, as well as the simulation and AI-based data generation tasks.

6.1.2 Sensors

Most datasets described clearly the sensor modalities that were used to perform the recordings. As depicted in **Figure 19**, cameras, lidars, and IMU/GNSS sensors are the most used sensor modalities with cameras being used in almost all datasets.

Figure 19 Sensor modalities in driving datasets

Most datasets use RGB cameras, while other types including 3D and fish-eye cameras are reported by several datasets (Figure 20). However, a variety of other sensors is considered by some datasets which could prompt the community towards exploring a wider sensor suite to enhance perception. The diversity of sensor modalities has been shown to enable more robust and accurate perception by compensating for the limitations of individual sensors (e.g., cameras struggling in poor lighting, or lidars in heavy rain). Nevertheless, the fusion of heterogeneous sensor data presents challenges, including temporal synchronisation, spatial calibration, and the necessity of advanced fusion algorithms to manage conflicting or ambiguous information. Notwithstanding the intricacies involved, the integration of diverse sensor types is instrumental in the development of resilient and dependable autonomous systems. In the synthetic datasets the prevalent choice is the usage of one lidar, while two datasets report one additional infrastructure lidar.

Figure 20 Camera types used in driving datasets

6.1.3 Annotations

The distribution of annotation types across existing datasets is depicted in Figure 21. The horizontal axis represents the number of datasets, while the vertical axis lists the different types of annotations.

Figure 21 21Annotation types of driving datasets

The most used annotation types are 3D bounding boxes (31 datasets). Other frequently used annotations include lane markings/ road paintings, trajectories and traffic signs, each occurring in about 20 to 30 datasets. Less common annotations include 2D bounding boxes, drivable areas, road conditions, key points (human pose) and semantic segmentation appearing in 10 to 20 datasets. Categories such as camera pose, 2D video panoptic segmentation and anomalies/outliers appear in fewer than 10 datasets each. In half of the synthetic datasets only three annotation categories are provided, namely 2D bounding box, 3D bounding box and semantic segmentation, showing much less diversity compared to the real driving datasets. The chart highlights the variety of annotations used across datasets, emphasizing the predominance of spatial annotations like 3D bounding boxes while showing the uniqueness of more specific annotations like panoptic segmentation or anomaly detection.

Figure 22 Datasets22illustrates the top 10 datasets with the highest number of available annotation types. The horizontal axis displays the names of the datasets in descending order of their annotation variety, while the vertical axis represents the number of annotation types available in each dataset.

Figure 22 Datasets22 with most available annotation types

The datasets “Kitti360” and “Argoverse” cover most of the annotation types, offering a total of 11 annotation types. They are followed closely by “PIE” and “MONA”, which provide 9 annotation types. “INTERACTION”, “nuPlan” and “Waymo perception” include 8 annotation types. The number of annotation types decreases more in the following datasets “OTOH/WOVEN Toyota”, “L1-L2 ADAS” and “DLR-UT” with 7 annotation types.

This chart highlights the diversity of annotations provided by these datasets. “Kitti360” and “Argoverse” stand out as the most versatile datasets in terms of annotation variety, while “DLR-UT” or “L1-L2 ADAS” have the fewest annotation types among the top 10 datasets. These insights are particularly valuable for guiding dataset selection based on the specific requirements of various research or application domains. For instance, tasks involving multi-modal learning, behavior prediction, or complex scene understanding benefit significantly from datasets that offer a diverse set of annotation types. Conversely, more focused applications—such as traffic sign detection or lane keeping—may require only a subset of annotations. By highlighting both the distribution and richness of annotations, this analysis supports informed decision-making in dataset choice, ensuring alignment with the technical goals and constraints of a given project.

6.1.4 Environment

The collection of the environment related information was not always straightforward as many datasets do not provide all aspects requested by our taxonomy. Most of the real driving datasets have been collected in Europe followed by North America and Asia, as illustrated in **Figure 23** Geographic distribution of driving datasets

Figure 23 Geographic distribution of driving datasets

In terms of road type, datasets collected under urban environment hold the first place (49 out of 60 datasets - 82%) followed by highways (40%) and last rural (27%) (Figure 24). Several datasets that focused on intersections were found (60%) while those including roundabouts are significantly less (20%). It should be noted that many datasets provide recordings in more than one road types.

Figure 24 Road type distribution of real driving datasets

The majority of the datasets were collected under good weather and light conditions. However, the datasets that include recordings under adverse environmental conditions may be of increased interest for SYNERGIES, as they represent more challenging scenarios. These include weather, visibility and road conditions which may compromise the perception and/or the control of the vehicle. As illustrated in Figure 25, rain (45%) is the most common adverse weather condition reported in the found datasets followed by fog (28%), wind (20%) and snow (20%). Less

than half of the datasets report night recordings (38%) while much less report recordings under wet (18%) or icy road (8%) conditions. Finally, about 25% of the datasets report recordings under reduced visibility conditions.

Figure 25 Adverse environmental conditions in real driving datasets

The above findings indicate a potential gap in the driving datasets field in terms of coverage of challenging environmental conditions such as adverse weather or reduced visibility. Moreover, not all possible conditions are captured in the found datasets, for example compromised visibility due to strong sun or reflections. Enrichment of the dataset field in this direction is important and may constitute part of the focus of the SYNERGIES data collection and generation campaigns.

6.1.5 Size

The size of driving datasets is usually disclosed by the data provider; however, diverse units of measurement may be used, which can render comparisons between datasets difficult. Size information may be provided through the:

- Number of Scenes: The distinct locations or episodes captured in the dataset.
- Total Number of Frames: The total frames recorded, often tied to sensor data.
- Total Recorded Time (Hours): The duration of the recording.
- Total Recorded distance (km). Specific to moving Point-of-View datasets
- Number of Recorded object Trajectories: The count of distinct obstacle movements tracked within the dataset.

Most datasets report their size using one of these units, though some may provide multiple metrics, while others provide little or no information at all (**Figure 26**).

Figure 26 Distribution of datasets used units

The reported size of the qualified datasets in terms of number of scenes varies significantly in a range between 50 and 1500 scenes of diverse length. Most of the datasets have relatively low storage volume, inferior to 50GB, with the exception of two datasets with storage volume superior to 1 TB. However, publicly disclosed information on dataset size is neither uniform nor precise, making direct comparisons across datasets challenging. A more accurate understanding would require downloading and thoroughly analyzing the datasets. This will be performed during the selection and processing of datasets for the creation of scenarios and the other data-dependent tasks of SYNERGIES. Based on the available metadata, such as the number of scenes and storage volume, we can infer that most open datasets are relatively limited in size. This is consistent with their intended purpose to serve as testing resources rather than exhaustive or fully representative samples of real-world scenarios.

One potential reason for the observed diversity in size documentation is that the choice of units used to measure a dataset's size often depends on the dataset type or its main purpose. For example, perception-focused datasets often use the number of frames as the primary unit, as the emphasis is on analyzing sensor data like LiDAR or camera images. On the other hand, path planning or trajectory prediction datasets may report size in terms of the number of object trajectories, reflecting their focus on movement patterns and predictive modelling. At the same time, even when dataset size is disclosed as generic metadata, several ambiguities may arise including:

- *Are scenes of fixed length?*
If so, what is the duration or other criteria defining a "scene"? Without this clarification, the term "scene" can vary greatly between datasets, complicating comparisons.
- *How is the number of frames calculated?*
Is it a combined total from multiple sensors (e.g., cameras, LiDAR, radar)? If so, does this count include overlapping or redundant frames? Alternatively, does it represent only annotated frames, or a mix of annotated and raw data?
- *Are trajectories provided independently?*
When trajectory data is included, it is often unclear if trajectories are independent entities

(e.g., distinct objects or events) or if they overlap or correlate. This lack of detail can make trajectory analysis inconsistent across datasets.

The above observations are important for SYNERGIES as they provide insights regarding the selection of the correct size units and documentation process to best report the size of the datasets that will be collected within the project.

6.1.6 Driving mode of ego car

For the real driving datasets that were recorded using one (or more) ego vehicles, a disparity in the driving mode of the vehicle(s) used is noticed. Some datasets explicitly report using an AD vehicle while others a manual driving vehicle (human driver). Although most datasets do not explicitly report this information it could often be derived indirectly from the described data collection process or the reported vehicle models. As illustrated in **Figure 27**, most datasets were recorded on manual driving mode. This is not surprising since in many parts of the world, the operation of ADS on public roads is not allowed or requires special authorization procedures. However, data collected by ADS may be of increased interest for SYNERGIES in terms of scenario creation.

Figure 27 Distribution of datasets per driving mode

6.1.7 Simulation software

All qualified synthetic datasets used CARLA as their main simulation software. Its common usage is related to its capability of simulating several aspects, from traffic agents, to photorealistic environment conditions, infrastructure, and physics dynamics. Three datasets employed co-simulation using CARLA together with SUMO and/or OpenCDA (**Figure 28**). Co-simulation approaches provide enhanced capabilities, including thorough traffic simulation, implementation of V2X communication and on demand capabilities within a scenario, which are not provided directly by one software tool. Due to the very low number of synthetic datasets considered, the above observations may not represent correctly the general field of synthetic datasets for ADS. Many more simulation tools exist, which may be interesting to explore within SYNERGIES to support the generation of high-quality realistic data and scenarios.

Figure 28 Simulation software packages used per synthetic dataset

6.2 Accident report datasets

Nine out of the eleven accident report datasets passed the qualification and were further analyzed. Due to their low number, a comprehensive analysis per taxonomy field is not meaningful, hence an overview of the main characteristics of these datasets will be discussed here. Most datasets include accidents within a specific geographic location or country in Europe (Germany, France, United Kingdom) or the USA, except for IGLAD [73] that covers a wide range of locations across continents (iError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.). Six datasets are based on police reports, one dataset (NHTSA accident data for ADS and Level 2 [71]) is collected by manufacturers and operators of vehicles equipped with ADS, one dataset (SHRP2 [69]) includes accidents recorded by a large fleet of instrumented vehicles, and finally one dataset (GIDAS [72]) is generated within the traffic accident research. All datasets include fatal accidents and concern accidents occurring in any road type and under all possible environment and lighting conditions. Hence, the severity and environmental coverage of each accident report dataset is high. Six out of the nine datasets are validated, one is not validated and for two this attribute is not applicable.

The accident report datasets may contain information at macro level, based on general statistics reported by the authorities, or at micro level, in which more details of the accident are provided, either via in-depth investigations or by extension of the macro level data. On macro level, most EU countries report road accidents in cases where there is at least one injured person, although there is no harmonisation on the reporting criteria for the injury level. Some examples of those databases are STATS19 (England) or BAAC (France). These datasets provide a good coverage as they are generally issued or owned by the national authorities, but the level of details and quality provided may be limited. On the other hand, accident data at micro level, are usually collected by experts based on in-depth investigations (e.g. GIDAS, VOIESUR, iGLAD), including in some cases even medical data, or contain extended information from the accident data at macro level, such as trajectory information (e.g. TASC). These datasets are usually richer in their content and have dedicated processes for data collection, which enhance their quality, although they usually have limited coverage, due to the high effort required to collect them. For SYNERGIES, both levels of detail are relevant as they can complement each other on the detailed information provided and on the coverage. Further work is needed to ensure their representativeness, a topic which is addressed under Task T6.1.

Accident report datasets that provide information at micro level, can serve several purposes, such as scenario-based approach evaluation, ADS design, safety case demonstration, and type approval compliance. At the moment, this work is only performed manually and case by case by road safety experts. Some of these accident datasets can provide specific weighting parameters, allowing to have a representativity of the sample at a larger geographical level (e.g. national level), for the corresponding year of the survey.

What is important from the accident datasets for their use in SYNERGIES is their coverage at functional and logical scenarios level. The objective is to build or (re)use a taxonomy that allows to cover 99% of European injured accident cases and to identify all pertinent tags for filtering relevant scenarios via a query.

6.3 Conclusions

Our analysis targeted 69 datasets coming from external sources which have met the quality criteria of SYNERGIES. From these, 60 are driving datasets and nine are accident report datasets. These datasets shall be considered by SYNERGIES as sources for the identification, extraction, and generation of scenarios, as well as for other tasks such as AI-based data generation, extraction of statistical information and development of tools. Apart from their technical utility, analysis of the existing datasets field reveals the status of their current coverage and the gaps that the project may choose to target through the foreseen data collection and generation campaigns. The above analysis aimed to address both these aspects.

The driving datasets were analysed based on the respective taxonomy designed in this task (Chapter 4), specifically the sensing domain, the sensor suite, the environmental conditions, the included annotations, the size, and the driving mode (for real data) or simulation tool (for synthetic data). These features constitute an informative overview of a dataset's main characteristics. Although most datasets were recorded from the ego viewpoint, other sensing domains such as infrastructure and drones were reported. Different sensing domains offer complementary benefits which may be leveraged if combined, a possibility that SYNERGIES could explore further. Camera sensors seem to be the most used sensing modality in the existing datasets followed by LIDARs. Most datasets used a sensor suite of multiple sensors per type and more than one sensor types which can improve the field of view and the accuracy of perception, due to the complementary features of different sensors. As desired this approach may be, it requires advanced processing tools for the fusion and synchronization of the sensor suite. SYNERGIES foresees the development of such tools and their inclusion in the Marketplace. Most datasets were recorded in urban environments which provide the opportunity for the identification of complex and challenging scenarios. However, rural datasets are significantly fewer, this highlighting a gap in the coverage which could be addressed by the data collection and generation campaigns of the project. Similarly, recordings in adverse weather and visibility conditions are underrepresented and could be enriched by SYNERGIES towards more challenging scenario creation. On the side of provided annotations, 2d or 3d bounding boxes are included in most datasets, which meets the SSD requirements, however, trajectories are not commonly provided. This may increase the effort needed for these datasets to be used for scenario creation. Datasets size is very variable and documented in various ways, rendering an overview of this attribute cumbersome. Finally, most real datasets were recorded by manually driven cars, however, recordings by ADS may be of increased interest as they capture behaviours that are not encountered in human driving but are relevant for the future of CCAM. For synthetic datasets, CARLA seems to be the prevalent simulation environment, while co-simulation using multiple tools is commonly used to decrease the sim-to-real gap, however

these observations may not be representative of the field due to the small size of qualified synthetic datasets.

The accident report datasets considered in this analysis were very few and very disperse, hence a detailed overview of their specific attributes was not possible. It is interesting that some of the accident report datasets provide more macroscopic information regarding the incident, while others dive into much higher levels of detail with the cost of covering fewer cases. Most accident datasets cover all road types, environmental conditions and severity levels, and have been validated, which ensures the quality and trustworthiness of their information. The collection of accident report data was mainly based on police reports while other sources of accident information were also identified.

Overall, the outcomes of this analysis highlight the main features and the coverage of the current state of existing datasets and shall inform SYNERGIES on potential pathways to the design of data collection/generation campaigns towards adding value to the field of ADS data and scenario creation.

7 METADATA

The qualification and analysis of the datasets generated several metadata attributes. The purpose of these metadata is to provide information regarding important quality features, as well as attributes of interest that can assist to the description and tracing of these data for more efficient usage. In this direction, we identify two types of metadata which we refer to as *analysis metadata* and *quality metadata*. The analysis metadata are the result of the analysis presented in Chapter 6 from which the most important attributes were selected. The quality metadata provide a measure of the effort required for the dataset to be used in SYNERGIES. This is related to the effort required to bring a dataset to the SYNERGIES scenario source data (SSD) format which is the merging point for all datasets prior to be used for scenario creation tasks. The decided SSD format for SYNERGIES is the Omega-prime format [3]. In the next sections, first a short summary of the Omega-prime format is presented, and subsequently, the analysis and quality metadata are described.

7.1 Overview of the SYNERGIES Scenario Source Data Format

In the context of SYNERGIES, SSD means a data model and a format for data that is to be used for scenario identification, extraction, enrichment, and generation, and their related activities. The data model defines which information (i.e., signals) must be present in the data and at what level of quality. The data format defines how the information shall be saved and exchanged. SSD must contain the following three types of information:

- Static information about the (road) infrastructure in form of a static map
- Dynamic information in form of time-stamped observations of
 - o Environmental conditions (e.g., precipitation)
 - o Road user-related information (e.g., states)

The *omega-prime* [3] specification defines a data model and format for SSD by leveraging the established standards ASAM OSI [7] and ASAM OpenDRIVE [8]. Omega-prime defines which subset of all possible signals in ASAM OSI are mandatory for the dynamic information part of the SSD. The ASAM OpenDRIVE standard is used for the static information part of the SSD. Additionally, omega-prime defines a data format using the MCAP [9] container format that allows to store and exchange SSD data.

7.2 Analysis metadata

The analysis metadata contain the main features that describe a dataset and shall facilitate the users to select and retrieve the datasets that can serve their needs. These metadata were derived through the analysis presented in Chapter 6 and are described below for each type of datasets. For the ease of visualization and usage, not all taxonomy attributes are reported as metadata.

7.2.1 Driving datasets

The attributes of the sensing domain, sensors, environment, and AD mode (for real) or simulator (for synthetic) were selected as the most crucial to report to guide the selection of the driving datasets. The metadata were clustered into the following categories:

1. **Real/Synthetic:** Denotes whether the dataset is real or synthetic
2. **Domain type** (MP, FP, B): Denotes whether the recording is from a moving point of view (MP) i.e. ego/vehicle sensing domain, fixed point of view (FP) i.e. infrastructure/drone/pedestrian sensing domain or includes both (B).
3. **Sensors** (C,L,R,G,O): Marks the sensor modalities used for recording and denotes camera all types (C), lidar (L), radar (R), IMU/GNSS (G), other types (O).
4. **Road type** (U,R,H,I,O,TS): Marks the road types where the recordings took place and denotes urban (U), rural (R), highway (H), intersection (I), roundabout (O), and test site (TS)
5. **Adverse weather** (yes/no): Marks the datasets that report recordings under rain, snow, fog, wind.
6. **Visibility reduced** (yes/no): Marks the datasets that report recordings during night, dusk and dawn.
7. **V2X** (yes/no): Marks the datasets recorded by two or more sensing domains as described in Section 4.
8. **AD mode/simulator** (yes/no or C, S, O): For real datasets it marks the dataset recording in AD mode and for synthetic datasets it denotes the simulation environments used as Carla (C), SUMO (S), OpenCDA (O).

7.2.2 Accident report datasets

For the accident report datasets, the selected metadata report the source of the data, a short description and the validation status. All qualified accident report data include all environmental conditions, hence the reporting of this information for each dataset did not provide added value.

1. **Source:** Describes the source of the data (e.g. police reports, accident research)
2. **Description:** Short description of the dataset in free text
3. **Validation status** (Validated, not validated, not applicable): represents the validation status of the scenario as described in Section 0.

7.3 Quality metadata

As discussed earlier, the datasets analysis and metadata generation refer solely to those datasets that have passed the qualification methodology. However, even if the datasets comply to the defined high-level quality criteria, the effort that is required for them to be leveraged within SYNERGIES might vary. This is captured by the quality metadata attribute "Distance to SSD" which reflects how much effort is needed to convert a dataset to the OmegaPrime format through comparison of the dataset's content with the content dictated by OmegaPrime. The distance to SSD is encoded into the following categorical values:

1. **Very close:** Conversion requires minimal effort, relevant signals (including map information) are available. In all such cases, object classification mapping may need to be performed.
2. **Close:** Conversion requires additional effort which is potentially worth to make for an otherwise promising dataset. Examples include extraction of trajectories from annotated objects, interpolation of annotations where keyframe frequency is lower than required, application of coordinate transforms and retrieval of maps in cases of well-defined recording areas.

3. **Moderate:** Conversion requires additional effort which needs to be weighted against the benefits of the dataset. Examples include the retrieval of maps in datasets without well-defined recording areas.
4. **Far:** Conversion requires significant effort, most probably beyond the benefits of using the dataset. Examples include datasets where maps and other information (e.g. environment conditions of recordings) is missing.
5. **Converted:** Some datasets have already been converted to the OmegaPrime format. This information is indicated in the metadata.

8 DATASETS FROM EXTERNAL SOURCES – FINAL LISTING

This chapter presents the detailed list of datasets from external sources that have passed the qualification criteria. The tables that follow list the datasets together with their metadata and their references.

Table 5 List of driving datasets with metadata

Dataset name	Real/ Synthetic	Domain type	Sensors	Road type	Adverse weather	Visibility reduced	V2X	AD mode/ Simulator	Distance to SSD
Nuscenes [10]	Real	MP	C,L,R,G	U	✓	✓		✓	Very close
Waymo perception [11]	Real	MP	C,L	U	✓	✓		✓	Very close
BDD100K [12]	Real	MP	C,G	U,H	✓	✓			Close
Zenseact [13]	Real	MP	C,L,G	U,R,H	✓	✓			Close
KITTI [14]	Real	MP	C,L,G	U,R,H					Moderate
DAIR-V2X [15]	Real	B	C,L,G,O	I	✓	✓	✓	✓	Very close
V2V4Real [16]	Real	MP	C,L,O	U,H,I			✓	✓	Moderate
WIBAM [17]	Real	FP	C	I		✓			Far
TUMTraf A9 Highway [18]	Real	FP	C,L	H	✓	✓			Moderate
TUMTraf Intersection [19]	Real	FP	C,L	I	✓	✓			Moderate
TUMTraf V2X [20]	Real	B	C,L,G	I	✓	✓	✓		Moderate
V2X-Real [21]	Real	B	C,L,G,O	U,I		✓	✓	✓	Very close
SemanticKITTI [22]	Real	MP	C,L,G,O	U,R,H,I,O					Very close
Argoverse 2 [23]	Real	MP	C,L,O	U,R,H,I,O	✓	✓		✓	Very close
UAVDT [24]	Real	FP	C	U,I	✓	✓			Very close
RADIATE [25]	Real	MP	C,L,R,G,O	U,R,H,I	✓	✓			Very close
KITTI 360 [26]	Real	MP	L,G,O	U,R,I,O		✓			Very close
PIE [27]	Real	MP	C,G,O	U,I		✓			Very close
Occ3D [28]	Real	MP	L	U,I	✓	✓		✓	Very close
View-of-Delft [29]	Real	MP	L,R,G,O	U,I	✓	✓			Very close
LUCOOP [30]	Real	MP	C,L,R,G	U			✓		Very close
highD [31]	Real	FP	C	H					Converted
exiD [32]	Real	FP	C	H					Converted
inD [33]	Real	FP	C	U,I					Converted

round [34]	Real	FP	C	R,O					Converted	
uniD [35]	Real	FP	C	U					Converted	
Argoverse [36]	Real	MP	C,L,G,O	U,H,I	✓	✓		✓	Close	
Nuplan [37]	Real	MP	C,L,G,O	U,H,I,O				✓	Very close	
MONA [38]	Real	FP	C,O	U,H					Close	
INTERACTION [39]	Real	FP	C,O	U,H,I,O				✓	Close	
JAAD [40]	Real	MP	C	U,I	✓				Close	
V2X-Seq [41]	Real	FP	C,L	U,I				✓	✓	Close
Waymo motion [42]	Real	MP	C,L	U	✓	✓		✓	Very close	
DLR-UT [43]	Real	FP	C	U,I	✓	✓			Converted	
DLR HT [44]	Real	FP	C	H	✓	✓			Very close	
UDRIVE	Real	MP	C,O	U,R,H,I,O	✓	✓			Far	
L1-L2 ADAS RENAULT	Real	MP	C,R,G,O	U,R,H,I,O	✓	✓		✓	✓	Very close
STELLANTIS	Real	MP	C,L,R,G,O							Moderate
CADCD [45]	Real	MP	C,L,G,O	U	✓				✓	Moderate
Talk2Car [46]	Real	MP	C,L,R,G	U,H,I	✓	✓			✓	Very close
OpenDD [47]	Real	FP	C,L	O						Close
METEOR [48]	Real	MP	C	U,R,H,I	✓	✓				Moderate
LostAndFound [49]	Real	MP	C	U						Moderate
Complex Urban [50]	Real	MP	L,G,O	U,I				✓		Moderate
MVSEC [51]	Real	MP	C,L,G	U,R,H,I	✓	✓				Moderate
TAF-BW [52]	Real	FP	C,O	U,I						Very close
VERI-Wild [53]	Real	FP	C	U	✓	✓				Moderate
VLMV [54]	Real	FP	C,O	H				✓		Moderate
SODA10M [55]	Real	MP	C	U,I,O	✓	✓				Moderate
OTOH/WOVEN [56]	Real	MP	C,L,R	U,I,O	✓				✓	Moderate
DSEC [57]	Real	MP	C,L,G	U						Far
RadarScenes [58][58]	Real	MP	C,R	U	✓					Moderate
I see you [59][59]	Real	FP	C	U						Moderate
Boreas [60]	Real	MP	C,L,R,G,O	U,R,H,I	✓	✓			✓	Moderate
OPV2V [61]	Synth	B	C,L,G	U,R,H,I					C,S,O	Very close
CODD [62]	Synth	FP	L	U,R					C	Moderate
COMAP [63]	Synth	FP	C,L	U,I					C,S	Very close
V2XSet [64]	Synth	B	C,L	U,I					C,O	Very close

DOLPHINS [65]	Synth	B	C,L	U,R,H,I	✓			C	Moderate
SynWoodScape [66]	Synth	MP	C,L,R,G	U				C	Far
Hi-Drive [67][67]	Real	MP	<i>Waiting for information from projects</i>						
EVENTS [68][68]	Real	MP	<i>Waiting for information from projects</i>						

Table 6 List of accident report datasets with metadata

Dataset name	Source	Description	Validation status	Distance to SSD
SHRP 2 [69]	Accidents recorded with a large fleet of instrumented vehicles	Accident data, Incident data, driving data	Not applicable	Moderate
Road Safety Data - STATS19, 2020 [70]	Police-reported data	UK accident data	Validated	Moderate
Standing General Order on Accident Reporting NHTSA [71]	Manufacturers and operators of vehicles equipped with ADS/ADAS	Accident reports involving ADS/ADAS systems.	Not validated	Moderate
GIDAS [72]	Collection of accident data within the traffic accident research	German accident data	Validated	Moderate
IGLAD [73]	Police reported, Collection of databases (GIDAS etc.)	Global accident data	Validated	Moderate
TASC [74]	Police reported, Collection of data with AIMATS	Accident data (Germany/Saxony) and traffic scenarios	Not applicable	Close
BAAC [75]	Police reported accidents	National accident data France	Validated	Moderate
VOIESUR [76]	Police accidents reports from 2011	All fatalities and 20% of non-fatal RTC, France 2011	Validated	Moderate
ADScene_Accident [77]	Police accidents reports from 2011	10 (TBC) accident scenarios from ADScene Demo pack, extracted from VOIESUR database.	Validated	Moderate

9 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents the current state-of-the-art of existing datasets in the field of automated driving. Sources of existing datasets were systematically reviewed including publicly available datasets, projects relevant to SYNERGIES with potential to provide useful datasets, and SYNERGIES partners willing to share own datasets. As a first step, the quality of the collected datasets was assessed using the SYNERGIES high-level data qualification methodology, and a quality pass or fail decision was assigned to each of the datasets. Those which passed the qualification were considered as a pool of datasets with potential for SYNERGIES and were further analysed to gain an overview of their main features. The dataset analysis was driven by taxonomies which were designed in the frame of the task to identify the attributes of interest, relevant to the scope of scenario creation. To facilitate the usage of the found datasets, metadata were generated to report the most important datasets features.

Our review identified 160 datasets out of which only 69 passed the qualification process. The majority were real driving datasets recording traffic scenarios from different sensing domains and under various road and environmental conditions. Very few synthetic driving datasets passed the qualification process and complement the driving data listing. The amount of accident datasets is lower, highlighting the need to increase efforts towards accident data collection. Most driving datasets are recorded by a sensor suite attached to a vehicle (ego car) in urban roads and under good weather conditions. However, we found a number of datasets that provide recordings in adverse environmental conditions which could offer more interesting scenarios. Rural roads and recordings under adverse weather and light conditions are less represented in the datasets field, a gap that SYNERGIES could address through the data collection and generation campaigns foreseen. Only 11 accident report datasets were identified, from which the nine qualified for further analysis. Accident data reports present a wide variety of formats and content and usually report a high volume of cases in low level of detail or a smaller number of cases in high level of detail. All datasets cover a variety of road types and environmental conditions, and the majority are validated. Hence, despite their low number they may still provide a useful resource for scenario creation, while SYNERGIES may address the shortage of accident report data through its data generation tasks to enrich this useful resource.

The output of task T3.2 and the present deliverable is a dataset listing including qualified datasets together with their metadata. The generated metadata reflect the main features of the identified datasets with the aim to facilitate users to select those relevant to their needs. Although the dataset listing includes only qualified datasets, this does not mean that these can be directly used within SYNERGIES. The SSD format, as a merging point of all data within SYNERGIES, imposes specific requirements and attributes which may not be explicitly provided, and further processing may be needed. Hence, each dataset will demand a certain level of effort to be used which is relevant to the effort of its conversion to the SSD OmegaPrime format. This is crucial for their selection as it may counterbalance their potential benefits. The quality metadata reflect this aspect and complement the analysis metadata discussed above.

This listing shall facilitate the consideration, selection and usage of the existing data resources by the different subsequent tasks of SYNERGIES and the general community. It shall also assist in the identification of gaps that can be targeted by the project towards enriching further data collections.

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A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
2D	Two dimensions
3D	Three dimensions
AV	Automated Vehicle
AD	Automated driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
ADS	Automated driving system
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative connected automated mobility
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EU	European Union
FPS	Frames per second
GB	Gigabyte
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
Hz	Hertz
IMU	Inertial measurement unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NDS	Navigation Data Standard
ODD	Operational design domain
OSI	Open Simulation Interface
PoC	Proof of Concept
RGB	Red Green Blue
SOTIF	Safety of the Intended Functionality
SSD	Scenario source data
SUT	System under test
TB	Terabyte
V2X	Vehicle to everything
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package